

The Culture Of Innovation In The Islamic Civilization And Its Applications In The Vocational Education And Training In The United Arab Emirates

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 08, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 09, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : The Culture, The Islamic Civilization, Innovation, Vocational Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6341863</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its applications in vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates, and one of the most important results was: Interest in innovation has become a necessity necessitated by the nature of the modern era, due to the importance of innovation in the fields of life, and to the role of innovators in changing history, and re- The formation of the world or reality, and the difference of vocational education and training completely different from academic education in terms of its objectives, patterns, levels, inputs and outputs. The difficulties facing the improvement of technical vocational education and training are the lack of equipment and materials designated for that, and came out with the following most important recommendations: Officials must establish special foundations and standards With vocational education and training programs to enable it to achieve its ultimate goal of preparing young people to enter the labor market, rehabilitating workers in the production and service sectors, and providing and developing material resources for vocational education and training to meet the needs of trainees and workers in vocational college.</i></p>

Introduction

We are in the era of acceleration and transformation, and the concepts of creativity and innovation have become major requirements in a rapidly changing world. Countries and institutions have kept pace with progress and development in all aspects: such as cultural, political, social and economic aspects, taking place in our world, paying attention to the potential and latent energies of their children, and trying to create appropriate conditions for investing these creative capabilities and innovative potentials through many means, which are available to achieve that.

This era witnessed the growing interest by specialists and researchers in the culture of innovation, as many research has tended to study the mental aspects of innovation, while other research concerned to study the variables that affect the motivation of innovation among individuals, and the measurement methods and development methods of the innovation to be a culture for the individuals of society through studying the characteristics and features of innovators .

Instilling a culture of innovation in the mindset of students and youth at all levels of education, cannot be achieved by accident, but rather requires diligent work based on the transformation towards a unique and distinct situation, and working to provide a stimulating environment for thinking and creative work, as well as working to unleash talent and creativity through leaders who are able to foresee the future. With all its details and formations, and working to turn it into reality by seizing available opportunities, responding quickly to changes with the required efficiency and effectiveness, and working to establish a culture of innovation .

The Messenger of Allah, prophet Mohamed's hadiths reflects the educational methods and through his guidance, may Allah's prayers blessing, and peace be upon him, of applying innovation culture in the education, and in raising generations of innovators throughout history through the prophetic directives and instructions brought by revelation, and in the light of which the Prophet of mercy, may Allah's prayers and peace be upon him, brought up the generation of creativity, innovation, pioneering and leadership .

As per the forgoing, countries seek to reveal the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its applications in the vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates.

The Research Problem:

The problem of the study lies in the possibility of applying the culture of innovation of the Islamic civilization in vocational training in the United Arab Emirates, where we have found out that the Islamic civilization encourages innovation in terms of moral and financial rights, through systems that support creativity and innovation, leading to the consolidation of creativity and innovation as a culture prevalent in the Emirati society. As per the forgoing, the study research problem tries to answer the following main question:

What is the role of the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its applications in the vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates? Many sub-questions emerge from the main question as follows:

1. What is the concept of innovation culture in the Islamic civilization?
2. How can the culture of innovation be applied in the vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates?

The Objectives of the Research:

The main objective of the research is to identify the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its applications in the vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates, and the following sub-objectives are derived from the main objective:

1. Identifying the concept of innovation culture in the Islamic civilization.
2. Studying the application of the culture of innovation in the vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates.

The importance of the research:

The importance of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its application in vocational education and training stems from the encouragement call of the Holy Qur'an for the creativity and innovation, and also the guidance of the Messenger of the Allah Mohamed, may Allah's prayers and peace be upon him, about paying close attention to upbringing and educating a generation of young innovators in various aspects of life. The Ministry of Education and vocational institutions also ensured that instilling a culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization in the mindset of the younger generation, as education based on creativity and innovation is the sole and only way to achieve the required change to catch up with the developed countries, and the importance of innovation in vocational education and training, which works to ensure the acquisition of knowledge and vocational skills in preparing a generation with different skills in various disciplines, the contribution of vocational education and training to face the challenges and changes in the internal and external environments, and paying attention to the human resources, which is one of the most important resources that institutions possess in the process of development and improvement to achieve the desired goals.

The Approach of the Research:

This research applies the descriptive approach, which is based on defining the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its applications, and the principles of vocational education and training, in general, in order to diagnose the research problem and presenting it in all its aspects. The research focuses on all aspects related to the culture of innovation, its applications, vocational education and training. In addition, this research adopts the analytical approach through the analysis of the relation between the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and the quality of the vocational education and training, the impact of the innovation culture on the quality of vocational education and training and its impact on youth in the United Arab Emirates, and to identify the reasons for students' reluctance to the vocational education and training, and to link education outputs to the needs of the labor market. Furthermore, the research relies on the historical approach to define the historical eras of the Islamic civilization and its applications in education, and the establishment and development of vocational education and training in the United Arab Emirates.

The plan of the research:

The First chapter: The innovation culture in the Islamic civilization

The First Topic: Concepts of innovation, culture of creativity and innovation, innovation in the Islamic civilization.

The Second Topic: The Quran verses and hadiths that encourage innovation.

The Second Chapter: The importance of vocational education and training and its impact on youth

The First Topic: The concepts of vocational education and training, its objectives, its importance, and the benefits it achieves.

The Second Topic: The Obstacles and difficulties facing the vocational education and training.

The Conclusion.

The Findings and recommendations.

The First chapter: The innovation culture in the Islamic civilization

The Preface and chapterization:

We can find many concepts related to the right and the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization, and Muslims have taken care of this culture and instilled it in the young generation, and there are varied and various types of evidence about that, and the relation between the concept of innovation and culture has received a lot of attention in Islamic civilization, and more details shall be explained in this chapter through the following topics:

The First Topic: Concepts of innovation, culture of creativity and innovation, innovation in the Islamic civilization.

The Second Topic: The Quran verses and hadiths that encourage innovation.

The First Topic: Concepts of innovation, culture of creativity and innovation, innovation in the Islamic civilization.

The Innovation is one of the concepts that many researchers have addressed, and innovation is the actual embodiment of these new ideas, putting them into practice and practical application by turning them into reality, and preparing well-thought-out and calculated work plans to manage innovative initiatives by providing the necessary resources to implement the suggestions presented. Then identifying performance measurement indicators to assess the extent of success in achieving the goals of those initiatives, and it also means the ability to create something new and bring it into existence, and thus innovation and putting ideas in the field of work, and these ideas can include all new products or services or operations within the scope of the institution or the country, as well as extending to include procedures, policies and methods of work .

The culture of creativity and innovation is characterized with many aspects. As some people dividing innovation into two main groups: The first group of these definitions defines the innovation, as a type of activity that distinguishes man from other creatures. This group thinks that creativity and innovation as an activity linked to the mental health of individuals, and their lives as it should be, while the second group thinks that innovation is any action that leads to a new creative production for those who surround the innovator or according to the knowledge of the people in a particular place and time .

Paying attention to innovation has become a necessity necessitated by the nature of the modern era, and this is due to the importance of innovation in the fields of life, and to the role of innovators in changing history and reshaping the world or reality, and despite the fact that innovation represents the reality of the civilized existence of man since Allah Almighty created him on this earth. However, the scientific research of the phenomenon of innovation was conducted very lately, and a distinction is made between creativity and innovation, as innovation is the mental ability that a person tries to produce an idea, a means, a tool, and a method that did not exist before, or mainly develop it without imitation, in order to benefit the society.

As for the innovation in the Islamic civilization, it aims to exert maximum effort in investing all available energies, potentials and capabilities, in order to reach the highest levels of benevolence for the long-term and immediate reconstruction, or outstanding performance to reach the highest levels of benevolence in intentions, actions and ideas in order to reach the summit during life, and the highest paradise after death, or the exploitation of all available energies, potentials and capabilities and investing them with the highest strings for a complete fusion between this world and the Hereafter .

As per the forgoing, the researcher believes that innovation is the ability of individuals within institutions or the country to create something new, and the ability to bring it to reality and implement it, and thus it may be products, services, processes, systems, or otherwise.

The Second Topic: The Quran verses and hadiths that encourage innovation.

The Holy Qur'an encourages thinking as a human necessity, and some Islamic scholars considered it an Islamic obligation. The reference to the necessity of thinking about the universe, souls, all things and all livings came in many verses in the Book of Allah, Almighty (The Holy Qur'an), which call for thinking, contemplation and speculation. Some of these verses are recited as follows:

The Citation: Allah, Almighty, says: Do not marry polytheistic women until they believe; for a believing slave-woman is better than a free polytheist, even though she may look pleasant to you, and do not marry your women to polytheistic men until they believe, for a believing slave-man is better than a free polytheist, even though he may look pleasant to you. They invite 'you' to the Fire while Allah invites 'you' to Paradise and forgiveness by His grace.¹ He makes His revelations clear to the people so perhaps they will be mindful." Allah, Almighty, says: "Can the one who knows that your Lord's revelation to you 'O Prophet' is the truth be like the one who is blind? None will be mindful 'of this' except people of reason.", Allah, Almighty, says: "Have they ever reflected on the wonders of the heavens and the earth, and everything Allah has created, and that perhaps their end is near? So what message after this 'Quran' would they believe in?" Allah, Almighty, says: "In their stories there is truly a lesson for people of reason. This message cannot be a fabrication, rather 'it is' a confirmation of previous revelation, a detailed explanation of all things, a guide, and a mercy for people of faith." Allah, Almighty, says: "Have they not travelled throughout the land so their hearts may reason, and their ears may listen? Indeed, it is not the eyes that are blind, but it is the hearts in the chests that grow blind." .

The Holy Sunnah encourages the innovation: through thinking and contemplation in many hadiths, including: The Prophet, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, says: "Think about the blessings of Allah and do not think about the Allah's self and features, or you will perish." It was narrated by Sheikh al-Tabarani in al-Wasat, and al-Bayhaqi in al-Sha'b. The hadith contains a clear encouragement to think, rather it directs us to the correct and purposeful thinking, and there are hadiths that were received on the interrogative forms of his saying, may Allah's prayers and peace be upon him, "Do you know who is the bankrupt?" He awaits the answer, as he encourages his companions to think collectively to generate the largest possible number of ideas and solutions, until finally he leads them to the stage of preparation to put the ideas into practice, as he did in the Battle of Badr and other situations.

- “The believer is very clever, intelligent and cautious”, narrated by al-Quda’i in “Musnad al-Shihab” (128), and cleverness, intelligence, caution, and thoughtfulness, are all characteristics and results of behavior on which the believer is raised and acquires his skills in positive thinking and strength in his personality.

Thus, innovative thinking becomes a civilized necessity, and Muslims are in dire need of innovation, as there are challenges facing the Islamic world .

As per the foregoing, the researcher thinks that the instructions of the Noble Qur’an and the Holy Sunnah of the Prophet are contemplation, speculation, foresight, seeking knowledge, thoughtfulness, consideration, prudence, which include mental abilities in each of them, and what is meant by that is to practice them in life, and to direct the implementation of consideration and consideration, and the use of different and various methods to think.

The Second Chapter: The importance of vocational education and training and its impact on youth

The Preface and chapterization:

The history of technical education in the UAE goes back to the academic year 1958/1959, when the first industrial school was opened in the Emirate of Sharjah. In the academic year (1964/1965), the Industrial School was opened in Emirate Dubai, then, in the academic year (1969/1970) the Industrial School in the Emirate of Ras Al Khaimah was opened. As for commercial education, its history goes back to the year 1965/1966 AD when the commercial department was opened at the Industrial School - Dubai. Technical education in the UAE received the attention of officials in the state, especially the Ministry of Education, and the Ministry has recently worked to push the growth of this education, and try to develop and modernize it, and the expansion of its schools to include all regions of the country. .

The First Topic: The concepts of vocational education and training, its objectives, its importance, and the benefits it achieves.

Vocational education and training differ completely from academic education in terms of its objectives, patterns, levels, inputs and outputs. This requires officials to set foundations and standards for vocational education and training programs to enable it to achieve its supreme goal of preparing young people to enter the labor market, rehabilitating workers in the production and service sectors, or raising their efficiency according to changing work requirements. It is expected that the focus on the element of alignment between the outputs of human resource development systems and programs and the development requirements and the needs of the labor market will become one of the natural outcomes of the effects of globalization on these systems and programs, and vocational training: A set of procedures or steps that would create appropriate conditions that would enable the trainee to identify concepts or theoretical, scientific and technical information related to work, and to acquire and develop practical skills for its performance, as well as to acquire positive attitudes, values, habits and behavior clearly required to perform the work.

Quality of Vocational Education and Training: The American National Institute defines the quality of education as the knowledge that the graduate of the educational process uses to solve issues related to the problems of the work field through the functions of the administrative process (planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling, while the quality of vocational training is defined as planned processes and methodology for assessing quality and improving them in employment and vocational training, and knowing their conformity with the specific levels and standards based on results, evaluation and capacity-building.

As per the forgoing, the researcher thinks that the vocational training is an organized process that takes place before or during work in the educational institution or outside, with the aim of developing individuals with knowledge, skills and attitudes related to the performance of their work, within approved standards that make them able to improve their performance, develop their experiences, and direct their behavior to enable them to achieve his work according to the form, specifications and quality required in the work output.

The Second Topic: The Obstacles and difficulties facing the vocational education and training.

The difficulties that disrupt the improvement of the technical education and vocational training are the lack of the equipment and materials designated to achieve the improvement, and also there may be a lack of information when teaching some curricula that are difficult to understand, and there may be a lack of experience of some faculty members, as well as the gap between the theoretical study of science and knowledge, and between the practical side of it in practical life, and thus this creates a kind of great concern about the quality of technical education and vocational training, which leads to the inability to keep pace with the rapid and continuous development, as this results in poor quality of outputs, and it is difficult to meet the needs of the labor market with the resulting development on Technical and industrial development in developed countries .

The Conclusion.

The research focuses on identifying the culture of innovation in the Islamic civilization and its relationship to technical education and vocational training in the United Arab Emirates, by identifying the concepts of innovation and innovation in Islamic civilization, and addressing the Qur’an verses, the noble hadiths that encourage innovation, and the concepts of vocational education and training, and its emergence in the Emirates

and its objectives and outputs to keep pace with the labor market and its continuous development and growth, as well as its effects on youth, identifying the difficulties and obstacles facing vocational education and training, and how to overcome them by focusing on the quality of education and vocational training, and the use of modern technology.

The findings:

1. Paying attention to the innovation has become a necessity in the nature of the modern era, due to the importance of innovation in the all fields of life, and to the role of innovators in changing history and reshaping the world or reality.
2. Numerous Qur'an verses and noble Prophetic hadiths indicate the urge to think and innovate, and the exploitation of individuals' latent energies and potentials in the Muslim community for to benefit the Islamic nation.
3. Vocational education and training is completely different from academic education in terms of its objectives, types, levels, inputs and outputs.
4. The difficulties facing the improvement of technical education and vocational training are the lack of equipment and materials dedicated to achieve the improvement process, and also there may be a lack of information and knowledge when teaching some curricula that are difficult to understand.

The Recommendations:

1. The Officials shall set principles and standards for vocational education and training programs to enable it to achieve its supreme goal of preparing young people to enter the labor market and rehabilitating workers in the production and service sectors.
2. The necessity of defining the strategic objectives of vocational education and training through the development of leadership and supervisory human resources for the vocational education and training sector in vocational colleges using modern methods.
3. Providing and developing material resources for vocational education and training to meet the needs of trainees and workers in vocational colleges.
4. Developing vocational education and training programs according to national, regional and international standards in order to continuously adapt to the labor market.

The Work Cited List, Bibliography and References:

The Holy Quran:

Surat Al-Baqarah, Verse 221.

Surat Ar-Ra'd, Verse 19.

Surat Al-A'raf, verse: 185.

Surat Yusuf, verse: 111.

Surah Al-Hajj, verse: 46.

The Arabic references:

Al-Basit (The Simple), Musa Ismail, (2009), the guidance of the Prophet Muhammad, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, in applying innovation and creativity culture in the education, **The Arabian Gulf Message**, No. (112), pp. 13-72.

Al-Jassim, Suleiman Musa, and Al-Marzouqi, Ibrahim Muhammad, and Ibrahim, Ibrahim Muhammad, (1992), vocational, Technical and University Education in the United Arab Emirates, **The Proceedings of The Officials Meeting in Technical, Vocational and University Education in the Member States of the Arab Bureau of Education for the Gulf States**, pp. 1-18 .

Habib, Magdy Mahmoud Fathi, (2018), **The Motivation of innovation, awareness, self-confidence, and orientation towards school as predictors of curiosity among a sample of primary school students**, Master's thesis, Institute of Arab Research and Studies, Cairo, Egypt.

Al-Raoush, Wael Taha Ahmed, (2017), The degree of application of the inclusive quality management standards in vocational training institutes in Jordan from the point of view of the members of the commission.

Al-Saeed, Abdi Mohamed, (2014), The Human Capital and Innovation in the Algerian Institution, **Muthanna Journal of Administrative and Economics Sciences (MJAES)**, Volume (4), Issue No. (10), pp. 262-276.

Shaaban, Iyad Abdullah Muhammad, (2020), **The Impact of Leadership Styles in Promoting a Culture of Quality: Creativity and innovation as a mediating variable among the institutions that won the King Abdul-Thani Prize for Excellence in Jordan**, Ph.D. thesis, College of Graduate Studies, Mutah University.

Al-Shahrani, Saad bin Ali bin Muhammad, (2020), Creativity in Islam: A legitimate vision, **The International Journal of Islamic Sciences**, Volume (4), Issue No. (1), pp. 254-228.

Al-Adwani, Khaled Mutahar, (2011), **The inclusive Quality in Vocational Education**, Quality and Accreditation Department, Ministry of Education, Yemen.

- Ali, Mahmoud Muhammad, (2002), "**Developing thinking skills through educational curricula**", Dar Al-Mujtamaa, Jeddah, p. 34.
- Al-Omariya, Salah Al-Din, (2008), "**Creative Thinking**", Al-Mujtamaa Al-Arabi Library for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Kandari, Tansim Ahmed, (2011), "**The Role of Educational Institutions that Apply and Do Not Apply Quality Concepts and Standards in Building and Supporting a Culture of Innovation, Creativity, Excellence and Entrepreneurship**", Master's Thesis, College of Administrative & Financial Science, Gulf University, Bahrain.
- Al Mazrouei, Sami bin Khater bin Mahkoom, (2019), Developing technical education and vocational training using the techniques of the Fourth Industrial Revolution to face the challenges facing Omani youth in the labor market, **studies in university learning**, Ain Shamsin University, Cairo, pp. 109-134.
- Nas, Mr. Mohamed Ahmed, (2006), Education and Training in Vocational Education Institutions: A Study of the Egyptian Reality in the Light of International Experience, **Strategic Planning Conference for Open and E-Learning Systems - A Framework for Excellence**, Ain Shams University, Cairo.

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